

DIRECTIONS OF INCREASING PRODUCT COMPETITIVENESS IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: Industrial enterprises are one of the important sectors of the national economy. At the same time, they are of great importance not only in the economy, but also in the social sector. The article discusses some issues of improving competitiveness and offers and recommendations for improving the competitiveness of products.

Key words: competitiveness, quality, economic factor, technological factor, international market, tax burden, productivity, domestic market.

Due to the liberalization of the current economy and the sharp development of competition among product manufacturers, the effective activity of enterprises depends primarily on reducing the cost of products, improving its quality, and effective sales of products on the consumer market. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. The decision of M. Mirziyoev "On measures to improve the activities of the Agency for Standardization, Metrology and Certification of Uzbekistan" states the following: Further improvement of the system of standardization, metrology and certification, systematic introduction of international standards and technical regulations, development of the base of national standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan for local products in order to increase competitiveness, as well as align the structure of "Uzstandart" agency with international requirements[1]: the priority tasks and directions of the Agency for standardization, metrology and certification of Uzbekistan should be defined as follows:

- ensuring their compliance with modern requirements and increasing their competitiveness in the foreign market by rapidly introducing international standards and technical regulations in the production of local products;
- wide implementation of modern systems of product quality management, primarily in exporting enterprises, and implementation of certification of industrial products according to international standards;

- creation of favorable conditions for exporting enterprises in matters of product certification, activation of cooperation with international organizations aimed at recognition of national certificates and conformity assessment results in the main export markets;
- further development of technical regulation and metrology systems, increasing their effectiveness in ensuring systematic control of the safety of sold

products; - introducing modern information and communication technologies, expanding the types of interactive state services provided to business entities and the population. It can be understood that ensuring the competitiveness of the products of industrial enterprises and identifying and analyzing the problems in it are relevant from all sides.

A number of expert scientists conducted research on the topic, and Sh.Sh.Shodmonov, U.V.G'ofurov stated that "competition consists of the conflict of economic interests of market entities, and it is a struggle between them to have higher profit and more utility [2].

In the textbook edited by N.Q. Yoldoshev and V.I. Nabokov, "Competitiveness is a definition that reflects the difference of a product from its competitor's product in terms of the degree of conformity to a specific social need and the cost of satisfying it. In capitalist countries, the term "competition" is rarely used in relation to a commodity. It is mainly applied to the economy of companies, industries, individual countries" [3].

Therefore, conducting more in-depth research on increasing the competitiveness of products in industrial enterprises appears as an important issue of the present day, and acquires not only scientific, but also practical importance.

As a research methodology, observing, economic analysis, statistical grouping, comparative and systematic analysis were used, studying the opinion of scientists on the directions of increasing product competitiveness in industrial enterprises.

Product competitiveness depends primarily on its quality indicator. In terms of market relations, product quality should be approached from the consumer's point of view, so that he has the opportunity to choose the most suitable product among the cultivated products.

Based on this, it is necessary to consider the competitiveness of production products and raw materials, taking into account several factors:

- economic factor, based on cost and price of the final product;
- technological factor, taking into account the future modernization of production;
- social factor, taking into account the costs of a social nature when changing the direction of production.

Based on this, as noted, competitiveness is defined as the complex indicators that express the average consumer price of the product in the market, the means and methods of sale, and its consumer value, which are developed inside and outside the country and are acceptable to the consumer.

Research shows that in the future, the increase in the income of the population and the increase in purchasing power can increase the demand for the products produced in the country.

Taking into account the globalization of the economy at the present time, it is necessary to consider the problem of competitiveness in two directions:

1. Taking into account the sale of domestically produced products on the domestic market;
2. Taking into account the export of the product.

The analysis of the competitiveness of the products produced in the country shows that, taking into account the international market price, changes in the tax burden, and transportation costs (for example, equipment and technology, cotton fiber, fruits and vegetables), the competitiveness of the products is relatively high. Based on this, the following measures should be implemented to increase the competitiveness of the products and raw materials produced in the country:

- ✚ high-level use of production opportunities in the national industry, large-scale use of high-yielding varieties and their hybrids resistant to weather and climate conditions in agriculture, establishment of interregional exchange of purebred cattle and high-yielding crop types, strengthening of the machine and tractor fleet with new techniques and expanding the volume and types of purchase of equipment and tools through leasing;

- ✚ formation of ways of selling national products through new channels such as wholesale market, auction, stock exchange;

- ✚ limiting the importation of products produced in the country through import and limiting the volume of imports by product types and setting quotas for them, increasing the amount of customs payments for the volume of products imported in excess of the quota;

- ✚ in order to fully meet the demand of the country's population for food products, to increase the volume of production and processing of the product, to expand its assortment according to the demand of the population, to improve its quality and packaging;

- ✚ it is necessary to establish control over quality indicators in order to prevent harm to public health of imported food products;

- ✚ organization of product quality management in accordance with world standards and development of a system that guarantees the quality of food products and raw materials.

It should be noted that the competition itself is not enough to form the skill base of the production enterprise, it should be regularly expanded and improved.

The skill base enables the manufacturing enterprise to increase its competitiveness by keeping its state of innovation at a high level. Based on this, the process of ensuring competitiveness in industrial enterprises can be theoretically divided into two periods:

In the 1st period, it is necessary to form productivity factors (human factor capital, new knowledge, information, new technology, etc.), and to conduct this process in such a way that its result is at a high (maximum) level of productivity.

Phase 2: Large-scale implementation of formulated productivity factors.

Taking into account that today's production base is organized by private entrepreneurs, it is important to form and develop their skill base in order to ensure the competitive advantage of these forms of business management.

The skill base of these forms of economic management is primarily related to the level of knowledge of individual entrepreneurs and heads of private enterprises and other members involved in their management. It should be noted that most of the entrepreneurs who are working today do not have higher education. Most of those with higher education are not industry experts. Therefore, increasing their knowledge is important not only to increase the competitiveness of the products of entrepreneurs, but also to raise the economy of this industry in general.

World experience shows that in order to determine competitiveness, it is necessary to pay attention to organizational, economic, material and technical support and social conditions, in addition to property ownership. This is influenced not only by the participation of companies in the development of the national economy of one country, but also by the participation of transnational companies located in other countries.

The establishment of single free economic zones plays an important role in increasing competitiveness. The establishment of such regions provides an opportunity to receive additional funds due to the introduction of common customs rules, as well as to release competitive products to the market of other countries.

But we should pay attention to one thing, that the establishment of a single free economic zone requires the adaptation of national standards to world standards, and that the quality indicators of the produced products must meet international requirements.

The rapid development of AI technologies is based on the availability of cloud services, as well as a significant increase in public and private investments in this direction [4].

As a result of the rapid reforms carried out in our country, a number of positive results have been achieved in terms of production and competitiveness of industrial products. A number of statistics can be cited as proof of our opinion.

In conclusion, it can be said that increasing product competitiveness has become a natural factor in today's modern market. In order to ensure the consistent and stable development of product competitiveness in industrial enterprises, the development and precise definition of carefully and comprehensively based measures, important tasks and directions, programs of economic development at various levels for the next period

is a guarantee of success. At the same time, it is important to draw relevant conclusions by critically evaluating the progress and results of the previous period, and further improving the socio-economic development programs based on them.

Creating a competitive environment based on the effective use of the market mechanism requires the development of a number of scientifically based measures. These activities include:

- creation of an organizational and legal mechanism aimed at preventing a monopolistic situation in the national economy;
- strengthening relations with international scientific institutions in scientific research works;
- optimization of the market mechanism of the national economy complex based on competition.

In the theory of competitive advantage, production efficiency and competitive position are achieved through strategic planning, innovation, employee training, market research, introduction of technology that ensures resource efficiency, access to information and other factors. In order for the production enterprise to achieve this, first of all, it should have a qualified personnel base that can ensure the integration of the above-mentioned factors.

References:

1. On measures to improve the activities of the Agency for Standardization, Metrology and Certification of Uzbekistan, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoev, April 28, 2017, PQ-2935.
2. Shodmonov Sh.Sh., Gafurov U.V. Economic theory (textbook). - T., Science and technology, 2010
3. Yoldoshev N.Q., Nabokov V.I., Theory of Management, Textbook, T-2011
4. Бахромов Азизбек Алишер Ўғли ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЕМ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ // Colloquium-journal. 2022. №6 (129). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/vyzovy-i-perspektivy-upravleniya-razvitiem-tehnologii-iskusstvennogo-intellekta-v-uzbekistane> (дата обращения: 13.02.2023).